

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: SEIWOH****FIRST NAME: FATMATA LUCIA****PROGRAM CODE: DME****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: ONE****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did *not* use Zotero to insert references

The author did use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 0%

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

List your 5 key concepts:

1. How to write an excellent academic essay (EUCLID 2024,7-12)
2. Some rules of thumb for writing a paper (EUCLID 2024, 12-14)
3. American vs British English (EUCLID 2024, 24)
4. Plagiarism (EUCLID 2024, 33-39)
5. Style guide (EUCLID 2024, 40-42)

HOW TO WRITE AN EXCELLENT ACADEMIC ESSAY

1) INTRODUCTION

I enrolled for a Doctorate in Monitoring and Evaluation after nine years without studying. With the duration of no studies and an enormous workload (Career and family), I was overwhelmed and needed to learn how to juggle my time around many targets.

However, due to my determination to pursue this course, I embraced the reality, re-adjusted my schedule, and on February 2, 2024, I logged into the system to start the first course (ACA-401D). Interestingly, after registration, I still needed another two weeks to scribble through all the documents, videos, and materials to understand the course target.

I joined the course WhatsApp group on February 20, 2024, and witnessed other colleagues asking questions, raising concerns, and receiving feedback from the course instructor. The chats on the WhatsApp platform motivated me to revisit the deadline given to me by the university to conclude this first course, realizing that other students have already submitted two or more response papers.

English is the official language of Sierra Leone, where I come from, and Nigeria, where I am currently based. I have used the English language to study at primary and High school, for my bachelor's and master's degrees and in my work life. However, I have not assumed that I know it all. I know that at the Doctoral level, I will learn new styles of English language, writing, and work presentation.

The course pack for ACA-401/ACA-401D Period One has four main components (study material, videos including Basic ACA-401 Tutorial, Instructor's sample review video, Grammarly, and Zotero). Following my study of the ACA-4101D course pack of Period One and other study materials, I will prepare this response paper focusing on five key concepts: how to write an excellent academic essay, some rules of thumb for writing a paper, American vs British English, Plagiarism, and style guide in presenting academic papers.

2) HOW TO WRITE AN EXCELLENT ACADEMIC ESSAY

In the revised course pack for Period One of ACA-401D, essay writing is the first chapter discussed (EUCLID 2024). This chapter mentions many types of essays, but the focus here is on academic essays for academic purposes.

Different types of academic essays were highlighted and described in this document. Nonetheless, academic essays, no matter which type, have certain basic standards of formality, including formal prose register, citations, references, use of stable rhetorical moves, and advanced new contributions (EUCLID 2024, 7). The document also mentions basic steps in writing academic essays that all academic writing must respect to do good work (EUCLID 2024, 8).

The chapter indicates that academic writing seeks to provide answers to questions and pass on information on evidence-based ideas. To this effect, the process should follow a straightforward procedure. One must develop a personal plan with adequate time for conceptualization, research, studies, and consolidation of ideas in a structured manner. It is essential to define the essay question, which will serve as a guide and continuous reminder throughout the reading, searching, and writing process. Research, reading, note-taking, and referencing are essential to essay writing.

During research, it is essential to note that creative and critical thinking is required to help strengthen the evidence. The writer should be creative by expanding on their already existing ideas. On the other hand, critical thinking allows the writer to look at other studies, pieces of evidence, and work, justifying why and how such ideas contribute to your ideas.

An excellent academic essay must have three main parts: Introduction, body, and conclusion (EUCLID 2024, 10). The need to edit and reference academic essays using EUCLID standards was also highlighted.

These basic guidelines for writing good academic essays should help me throughout my studies at EUCLID. They will be helpful for a lifetime as I continue to write academic, work, and personal papers.

3) SOME RULES OF THUMB FOR WRITING A PAPER

This concept forms part of chapter one of the revised course pack Period One for ACA-401/ACA-401D. However, it is essential to write good essays and have decided to present them excellently. The course pack recommends eight thumbs in writing a good paper (EUCLID 2024, 13-14). When writing a good paper, one must stay focused after one has chosen a precise topic or view.

No matter the volume of information and opinions available or researched, the writer must stay focused on the particular view. Focusing on a specific topic affirms that every idea linked to the main area must be backed by evidence so that no sweeping generalities are made (EUCLID 2024, 13). Also, should there be other views for or against the central thesis, they must be evidence-based. All such views and pieces of evidence should be adequately backed by references and in a straightforward way to avoid plagiarism. The writer should take every new idea or view toward the main area with total concentration and understanding when writing a paper, which should be written clearly.

To motivate others to read and appreciate your paper, I agree that the writing should not be dull and clumsy (EUCLID 2024, 13); instead, make your work intriguing so the reader is motivated and interested in reading. Somebody can do this by avoiding long sentences and starting sentences differently.

4) AMERICAN VS BRITISH ENGLISH

There has always been American and British English, depending on the institution you work or write for. Sierra Leone, colonized by Britain, has used British English in all spheres. However, over the years, in my work life, I discovered that depending on the institution or country you are writing a paper for, you must ensure you specify and stick to one mode of the English language. Sticking to one mode of the English language is advisable because using American and British English in one document will create confusion, indicating typo errors when they are not, thus making one's work untidy.

However, this course pack goes deeper in providing examples and scenarios that would help us understand contexts in which you can use any of the two types of English language consistently.

5) PLAGIARISM

Plagiarism is using another person's work without acknowledging their efforts. Anyone who does such is equally not qualified to be an author. Plagiarism is an academic criminal offense culpable of punishment. This course pack teaches a new definition of plagiarism: when you allow someone else to prepare a paper on your behalf and submit it in your name as if it is your original work (EUCLID 2024, 34). I know this is corruption in the academic world, but I did not consider it plagiarism.

To prevent plagiarism, the writer can cite the author or source used to provide information, whether by direct quotes or paraphrasing (EUCLID 2024, 34-37).

6) STYLE GUIDE

A style guide documents your approach to some aspects of writing style that need consistency (EUCLID 2024, 41). Style guides are recommended for different publications so that the writer customizes her/her writing based on the type of publication done. Since there are clear guiding principles to respect, it is vital to remember that the writer follows the guidelines for the publication and the type of publication, not the writer's style, and there must be consistency.

For academic writing, one has to consider internationally recognized rules. However, for EUCLID University, the Chicago style is recommended. Chicago Style recommends Webster's Third New International Dictionary and Webster's Collegiate Dictionary for writing. Interestingly, I realized that the Chicago style proposes even spelling, which is severe but funny to ensure one's English is clean and smooth. As a result, the Chicago Manual of Style has a recommended website to which anyone can subscribe. In addition, Euclid University recommends American English.

7) CONCLUSION

It has been an intriguing start to a doctoral course as I read through the course pack and watched several videos before preparing this response paper. Going through all these tools has motivated me to press on with my studies and increased my curiosity to know what the coming sessions will unfold.

I will re-read and replay all these details since they are assets not only to my doctoral studies. I would have strengthened my capacity by the end of this study.

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